

Pragmatic and Metaphoric Aspects of Audio-Visual Ads

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Abstract

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This research article discusses and analyzes the pragmatic and metaphoric aspects of audio-visual advertisements, in this case pragmatic analysis dissects the metaphors contained in audio-visual advertisements. Advertising is a media promotion of a product or service. Advertising as a form of product or service information from producers to consumers and delivery of messages from sponsors through a medium. As a form of communication, advertising contains messages that can be conveyed through language (words) and images. Messages can be conveyed in various ways, including the use of pragmatic aspects and metaphors in advertisements, especially audio-visual advertisements. Advertising is an advanced communication process that brings audiences to the most important information they really need to know. The method used in this study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive-analytic method. The effectiveness of advertising depends on the structure and content of the message, hence the importance of pragmatic and metaphorical aspects in audio-visual advertising, in this case pragmatic analysis dissects the metaphors contained in audio-visual advertising.

1. Introduction

The term advertising in each country has a different meaning, the term advertising as a designation in Indonesia is different from the designations used in several countries in the world. That one example of the name of the ad in Arabic, in this case the ad is called I'Lan, while in the UK the name of the ad is called advertising, while in Indonesia it is called advertising. The ad word is taken from Arabic which is adopted into Indonesian because the pronunciation of the tongues of Arabs and Indonesians is very different. Every word conveyed in advertising media has a message to appeal to consumers (Cf. Fanggidae, 2019).

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Yule (2022) states that pragmatics is the study of meaning conveyed by speakers (writers) and interpreted by listeners (readers). In line with this opinion, Leech (2014) states that pragmatics is the study of meaning in relation to speech situations which include elements of the addresser and the person addressed, context, purpose, act of illocution, speech, time, and the place. So pragmatics is an interesting aspect of science to study because it involves how people understand each other linguistically, but pragmatics can be discouraging because this study requires that someone is able to understand what other people think about (Kusumarini et al., 2021).

Classe (2000:941) defines metaphor as transferring the image, meaning, or quality of an expression to another. The transfer is carried out by referring a concept to another concept to indicate similarities, analogies, or the relationship between the two concepts. According to Lakoff & Johnson (2008), the use of metaphor not only beautifies language, but can also be used for specific purposes depending on the situation. Metaphor is not just a linguistic expression, but also conveys in a conceptual system (Yadnya et al., 2021). Metaphors are not only found in literary works or poetic expressions, but also in everyday concepts. Like language, metaphor can also be a persuasive communication tool in everyday life. Nowadays advertisements in Indonesia tend to use metaphors in conveying messages. The main purpose of using metaphors in advertisements is to refine the way messages are conveyed so that they give the impression of being more artistic, polite and intelligent. In the end it will boil down to the quality and image of the advertisement in the eyes of consumers.

Advertising is a media promotion of a product or service. Pratiwi et al. (2022) explain the definition of advertising by referring to Jefkins' opinion. Advertising is a form of product or service information from producers to consumers and delivery of messages from sponsors through a medium. It was further explained that advertising is an advanced communication process that brings audiences to the most important information that they really need to know. A marketing expert, Kotler (2012), considers that the effectiveness of advertising depends on the structure and content of the message. Ideally, a message should get attention, attract interest, arouse desire, and cause action or also known as the AIDA model. In practice, only a few messages are able to carry consumers through all stages from awareness to purchase, but the AIDA framework shows the desired quality of each communication (Tandilintin, Y., & Amiruddin, 2021). This research article is discussing and analyzing the pragmatic and metaphorical aspects of audio-visual advertisements, in this case pragmatic analysis dissects the metaphors contained in audio-visual advertisements.

2. Materials and Methods

The research materials used in this research article are literature review materials in the form of books, scholarly articles, and/or scientific studies as well as expert opinions relating to pragmatic and metaphorical aspects of audio-visual advertising. The method used in this study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive-analytic method (Cf. Sujaya et al., 2021). The effectiveness of advertising depends on the structure and content of the message, hence the importance of pragmatic and metaphorical aspects in audio-visual advertising, in this case pragmatic analysis dissects the metaphors contained in audio-visual advertising.

3. Results and Discussions

Pragmatic and metaphorical aspects of audio visual advertising.

Pragmatics is the study of the relationship between language and the context that underlies the explanation of the meaning of language. Here, understanding or understanding language refers to the

fact that in order to understand a language expression or speech, knowledge is also needed beyond the meaning of the word and its grammatical relationship, namely its relation to the context in which it is used. Pragmatics is the study of the ability of language users to relate sentences with the appropriate contexts for those sentences (Cf. Sujaya et al., 2021). Pragmatics is also interpreted as conditions that result in the use of language in communication being harmonious or not; aspects of language use or external contexts that contribute to the meaning of utterances (Cf. Warmadewi et al., 2022). Warmadewi et al. (2022) state that pragmatics is a branch of linguistics that discusses what includes language structure as a means of communication between speakers and listeners, and as a reference to language signs on extralingual matters being discussed.

The Pragmatics aspect has certain studies or areas of study, namely diexistence, presuppositions, speech acts, and conversational implicatures. That pragmatics is the study of meaning conveyed by speakers (writers) and interpreted by listeners (readers). In addition, pragmatics can be understood as a study of meaning in relation to speech situations which include elements of the addresser and the addressee, context, purpose, act of ilocation, utterance, time and place.

Presupposition comes from the word to pre-suppose, which in English means to suppose beforehand, in the sense that before the speaker or writer says something he already has previous conjectures about the other person or thing being talked about. In addition to these definitions, several other definitions of presupposition include: Levinson provides the concept of presupposition which is aligned with presupposition as a kind of assumption or background knowledge that makes an action, theory, or expression have meaning. Yule (2022) states that presupposition or presupposition is something that is assumed by speakers as events before producing an utterance. Those who have presuppositions are speakers, not sentences.

Sani et al. (2021) state that presuppositions are assumptions or inferences implied in certain linguistic expressions. They provide an understanding of presupposition as the basis or basic inference regarding the context and situation of language (using language) which makes language forms (sentences or expressions) have meaning for listeners or recipients of that language and vice versa, helps speakers determine the forms language that can be used to express the intended meaning or message.

Speech acts are part of pragmatics. Speech acts, according to Bayat (2013), is the utterance of a sentence to express so that the speaker's intention is known to the listener (Cf. Dayter, 2021). Speech acts are utterances made as part of social interaction. According to Dayter (2021), speech acts are part of speech events, and speech events are part of speech situations. Every speech event is limited to activities, or aspects of activities that are directly governed by rules or norms for speakers. An utterance or speech act may consist of one or more speech acts in a speech event and speech situation. Thus, utterances or speech acts are highly dependent on the context in which the speaker speaks. New utterances can be understood only in relation to the activity in the context and place where the utterance takes place. In accordance with the opinion of Alwasilah (1993:20) that utterances are context dependent (depending on context).

The concept of implicature was first introduced by H.P. Grice (Cf. Davies, 2007) to solve the problem of language meaning which cannot be solved by ordinary semantic theory. Implicature is used to take into account what is suggested or what is meant by the speaker as different from what is literally stated by Yule (2022). On the other words, implicature are expressions indirectly, namely the meaning of the expression is not reflected in the vocabulary literally. According to Grice (quoted by Davies, 2007), in the use of language there are implicatures called conventional implicatures, namely implicatures determined by the 'conventional meaning of the words used'.

Metaphor is a transfer of image, meaning, or quality of an expression to another. The transfer is carried out by referring a concept to another concept to indicate similarities, analogies, or the relationship between the two concepts. According to Lakoff & Johnson (2008), the use of metaphor not only beautifies language, but can also be used for specific purposes depending on the situation. Metaphor is not just a linguistic expression, but also conveys in a conceptual system. Metaphors are not only found in literary works or poetic expressions, but also in everyday concepts. Like language, metaphor can also be a persuasive communication tool in everyday life.

Pragmatic and metaphorical aspects of audio-visual advertising, in this case the metaphor of audio-visual advertising in an advertisement using a pragmatic approach. Advertising promotes something positive. An advertisement uses a metaphor in conveying a message about the purpose of promoting the advertisement or the product. Audio visual advertisements describe the sequence of themes, types and meanings of metaphors based on the context behind them, that audio visual advertisements are loaded with metaphors if the sequence of themes in the schematic composition of an advertisement contains metaphors that convey certain concepts based on similarities or comparisons. In the pragmatic and metaphorical aspects of audio-visual advertising, in this case, it can be in two categories, namely inanimate (not alive) and animate (living), each of which has a meaning.

The pragmatic and metaphoric aspects of audio-visual advertising can be used as a pragmatic analysis of various audio-visual advertising products, for example cultural promotion to understand the messages and meanings contained therein. That metaphor is not just a decorative ornament, it also has a "compelling" function. Even though examining different objects, the function of "force" can be found in audio visual advertisements. It's just that there are differences in the way of conveying messages through the metaphors used, audio-visual advertising can be applied using a more subtle, figurative and philosophical delivery. Audio-visual advertising can only inform the product that will be sold by bringing the audience to the most important information that potential consumers really need to know.

4. Conclusion

Pragmatics has a particular study or field of study, namely diexist, presuppositions, speech acts, and conversational implicatures. That pragmatics is the study of meaning conveyed by speakers (writers) and interpreted by listeners (readers). In addition, pragmatics can be understood as a study of meaning in relation to speech situations which include elements of the addresser and the addressee, context, purpose, act of ilocation, utterance, time and place. Metaphor is a transfer of image, meaning, or quality of an expression to another. The transfer is carried out by referring a concept to another concept to indicate similarities, analogies, or the relationship between the two concepts.

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